

Tutorial for using hydroPSO to calibrate GR4J

Study area: Trancura River Basin, Chile

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v0.5 - May 31th, 2026

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1 A bit of history

When `hydroPSO` (Zambrano-Bigiarini & Rojas, 2013) started to be developed in 2010, to the best of our knowledge, `topmodel` was the only hydrological model fully implemented as an R function and available from CRAN. At that time, many operational hydrological and environmental models were still distributed as external executables, often requiring command-line interaction, text-based input files, and model-specific calibration workflows. Therefore, the initial development of `hydroPSO` focused on optimising hydrological and environmental models that run executable files from the command line of any operating system (OS, e.g., GNU/Linux, Windows, macOS), while also allowing the optimisation of R functions in a way that is conceptually compatible with `optim`, but oriented towards global rather than local search.

Since then, R has continued to gain visibility and adoption in the hydrological community. Several hydrological models are now fully implemented as R functions, even when some of them internally call Fortran or C/C++ routines. Examples include `TUWmodel`, `airGR`, and `VICmodel`¹. This transition has made it easier to build transparent, scriptable, and reproducible calibration workflows entirely within R.

This tutorial shows how to use `hydroPSO >= 0.5-0` to calibrate the lumped `GR4J` hydrological model using hydrometeorological input data included in the `hydroPSO` package. With basic R knowledge, the same workflow can be adapted to other catchments, alternative data sources, and other hydrological models implemented in R. In this sense, the vignette is intended not only as a worked example for `GR4J`, but also as a template for adopting `hydroPSO` in reproducible hydrological modelling studies.

2 Citation

This tutorial is based on the vignette showing how to use `hydroPSO` to calibrate `TUWmodel`, with modifications mainly related to the description of the hydrological model and its parameters, as well as to the specific way in which `GR4J`, through `airGR`, handles input time series and model outputs. If you find this vignette useful, please cite it as:

Zambrano-Bigiarini, Mauricio (2026). Tutorial for using `hydroPSO` to calibrate the `GR4J` hydrological model (version 0.4). doi:10.5281/zenodo.20476742. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20476742>.

3 Required `hydroPSO` version

This tutorial was developed for `hydroPSO >= 0.5-0`, released in Github in March 2020. Although `hydroPSO` has always been able to optimise any R function, its early versions were originally designed with external hydrological and environmental models in mind. Consequently, versions lower than `0.5-0` only keep track of goodness-of-fit values, and not the complete model simulations, when calibrating an R-based model. Since **v0.5-0**, `hydroPSO` is fully compatible with R-based hydrological and environmental models, including workflows where simulated time series are stored, analysed, plotted, and later used for uncertainty assessment.

4 Objective

The main objective of this tutorial is to show how to use `hydroPSO` to find an **acceptable** *best parameter set* for the `GR4J` hydrological model. The emphasis is practical and reproducible: defining model inputs, wrapping the model into a function suitable for optimisation, running the calibration, inspecting the calibration outputs, and using behavioural parameter sets for uncertainty analysis. The document is not intended to provide a complete discussion of hydrological concepts² or an exhaustive interpretation of the hydrological results.

The figures generated in this tutorial are therefore used mainly to illustrate the functionality of `hydroPSO` and the structure of a transparent calibration workflow. Their detailed hydrological interpretation is left to the

¹At the time of writing this tutorial, `VICmodel` had been removed from the CRAN repository on March 3rd, 2020.

²Some basic references are provided throughout the text to guide readers who are less familiar with topics such as calibration, verification, sensitivity analysis, and uncertainty analysis.

interested reader. The broader purpose is to demonstrate how `hydroPSO` can support rigorous, script-based, and reproducible model calibration studies that are attractive for hydrologists, water resources scientists, and developers of open-source modelling tools. Comments and questions are welcome.

5 `hydroPSO`

`hydroPSO` is a multi-OS and model-independent R package based on Particle Swarm Optimisation [PSO; Kennedy & Eberhart (1995)]. It was designed to support: *i*) model calibration; *ii*) sensitivity analysis; and *iii*) post-calibration assessment of model results. The package is compatible with calibration tools that use PEST-like files, can interact with external executable models, and can also optimise purely R-based model functions. This flexibility is particularly useful in hydrology, where modellers often need to compare models, objective functions, calibration periods, parameter ranges, and uncertainty assumptions within a consistent computational framework.

PSO is a population-based stochastic optimisation technique that explores a delimited parameter space with a *swarm* of particles. Each particle represents one candidate parameter set, and the swarm evolves to maximise or minimise a user-defined objective function. The search is guided by the best positions previously found by individual particles and by their neighbourhoods. Starting from random initial positions and velocities, the particles are iteratively updated until a user-defined stopping criterion is reached, such as a tolerance threshold or a maximum number of iterations.

For hydrological applications, this strategy is attractive because conceptual rainfall-runoff models often have non-linear parameter interactions, equifinality, and objective-function surfaces with local optima. `hydroPSO` provides a reproducible way to explore those parameter spaces, store model simulations, analyse behavioural parameter sets, and produce diagnostic plots that help evaluate calibration performance. For a detailed description of the `hydroPSO` package, please refer to Zambrano-Bigiarini & Rojas (2013) and Zambrano-Bigiarini et al. (2013).

6 GR4J hydrological model

The GR4J hydrological model, whose name stands for *modèle du Génie Rural à 4 paramètres Journalier*, is a daily lumped rainfall-runoff model developed by Perrin et al. (2003). It is based on a parsimonious soil moisture accounting structure and was designed to provide robust streamflow simulations using a small number of parameters. GR4J is the result of a sequence of developments that followed the original GR3J model (Edijatno et al., 1999). One of its key modifications is the introduction of a percolation function from the production storage, which improves the representation of low-flow dynamics relative to GR3J.

The model first combines precipitation (P) and potential evapotranspiration (E) to determine either net rainfall (P_n) or net evapotranspiration capacity (E_n), assuming an interception storage with zero capacity. When P_n is positive, a fraction P_s contributes to filling the production storage in the upper soil profile as a function of the current storage state (S). When E_n is positive, the actual evaporation rate (E_s) is computed as a function of the water stored in the production reservoir. After the production storage is updated, percolation leakage ($Perc$) is computed as a non-linear function of the storage state.

The effective water available for runoff generation, defined by percolation plus the fraction of net rainfall not retained in the production store, is then split into two routing components. Ninety percent is routed through unit hydrograph UH1 and a non-linear routing store, whereas the remaining 10% is routed through unit hydrograph UH2. These two unit hydrographs represent the temporal redistribution between rainfall and discharge response, including the delay between precipitation events and streamflow peaks. Total runoff is finally obtained by combining both routed flow components.

The parameters used by GR4J to represent the main catchment-scale hydrological processes are summarised in Table 1 and described in detail by Perrin et al. (2003). The 80% confidence intervals used here to define reference calibration ranges were also taken from Perrin et al. (2003) and are shown in Table 1. Because the model has only four parameters, GR4J is particularly useful for illustrating the capabilities of `hydroPSO`: the

calibration is computationally tractable, but still involves non-linear parameter interactions and trade-offs among hydrological signatures.

ID	Description	Units	Process	Range
X1	Maximum capacity of production storage	mm	ET, percolation	[100.0, 1200.0]
X2	Groundwater exchange coefficient	mm	Groundwater, routing	[-5.0, 3.0]
X3	One day ahead maximum capacity of routing store	mm	Soil storage, Routing	[20.0, 300.0]
X4	Time base of unit hydrograph UH1	day	Peak flows	[1.1, 2.9]

Table 1: Parameters used by GR4J to represent the different hydrological processes in a basin.

7 Installation

Install the latest stable versions of `hydroPSO` and `airGR`.

```
install.packages("hydroPSO")
install.packages("airGR")
```

Alternatively, you can install the development version of `hydroPSO` from GitHub:

```
if (!require(devtools)) install.packages("devtools")
library(devtools)
install_github("hzambran/hydroPSO")
```

Install the latest stable versions of `hydroTSM` and `hydroGOF`. These packages are used to manipulate hydrological time series and evaluate the performance of the simulated streamflow.

```
install.packages("hydroTSM")
install.packages("hydroGOF")
```

8 Model set up

8.1 Loading required packages

The `hydroPSO` and `airGR` packages provide the data and main functions used in this analysis. The `hydroTSM` (Zambrano-Bigiarini, 2026b) and `hydroGOF` (Zambrano-Bigiarini, 2026a) packages are used to manipulate hydrological time series and compute the modified Kling-Gupta efficiency [KGE'; Gupta et al. (2009); Kling et al. (2012)], respectively. Combining these packages illustrates a typical R-based hydrological workflow: data handling, model execution, objective-function evaluation, calibration, and post-processing within a single reproducible script.

```
library(airGR)
library(hydroPSO)
library(hydroTSM)
library(hydroGOF)
```

8.2 General settings

The variable `model.drty` is used as the parent directory where the output files generated during the calibration of the hydrological model will be stored.

```
# This object is defined in the initial setup chunk and can be modified there
# according to your specific local paths.
model.drty <- vignette.drty.out
```

The variable `PS0.drty.out` represents the output directory where `hydroPS0` stores the files generated during the calibration of the GR4J hydrological model. It is not necessary to create this directory before running the calibration because, if it does not exist, it is automatically created by `hydroPS0`. Keeping all optimisation outputs in a dedicated directory makes it easier to inspect parameter sets, objective-function values, model simulations, diagnostic figures, and log files after the calibration has finished.

```
PS0.drty.out <- file.path(model.drty, "PS0.out")
```

The variable `Figures.drty.out` represents the output directory where figures generated during the analysis of the calibration and verification results will be stored.

```
Figures.drty.out <- vignette.figures.drty.out
```

```
# If the output directory selected to store the figures does not exist, it is created:  
if (!file.exists(Figures.drty.out)) dir.create(Figures.drty.out, recursive=TRUE)
```

Set up the calibration (1979-1997) and verification (1998-2016) periods. Each period includes one year of model warm-up (see Section 9.2), which allows the internal stores of GR4J to adjust before the objective function is evaluated:

```
### Calibration period  
Cal.Ini <- "1980-01-01"  
Cal.Fin <- "1997-12-31"  
  
### Verification period  
Ver.Ini <- "1999-01-01"  
Ver.Fin <- "2016-12-31"  
  
### Starting date of the warm-up period, one for calibration and another for verification  
Warmup.Ini.Cal <- "1979-01-01"  
Warmup.Fin.Cal <- "1979-12-31"  
Warmup.Ini.Ver <- "1998-01-01"  
Warmup.Fin.Ver <- "1998-12-31"
```

8.3 Input data

The study area for this tutorial is a subcatchment of the Trancura River Basin, located in the Araucania Region of southern Chile. The catchment drains into the “Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco” streamflow station (COD.BNA:9414001). This basin provides a useful demonstration case because it combines a long daily hydroclimatic record with hydrological conditions that are suitable for evaluating rainfall-runoff model calibration.

To run GR4J, daily catchment-mean precipitation and potential evapotranspiration time series are required. Daily time series of precipitation (P [mm/day]), potential evapotranspiration (PET [mm/day]), and streamflow (Q [m^3/s]) for 1979-2016 were obtained from the CAMELS-CL dataset (Alvarez-Garretton et al., 2018). Precipitation corresponds to spatially averaged daily values from CR2met, whereas potential evapotranspiration was computed with the Hargreaves-Samani equation using maximum and minimum air temperature data.

All time series used in this example are included in `hydroPS0 >= 0.5-0`. The same workflow can nevertheless be applied to local data files, provided that the meteorological forcings and observed streamflow are read into R and transformed to the units required by the model and the objective function.

Specify the catchment area [m^2]:

```
Area.m2 <- 1415025887
```

Specify the name and ID of the discharge station used as the outlet of the study area. These values will later be used in figure titles during the analysis of the calibration results:

```
Qobs.stationname <- "Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco"
Qobs.ID          <- "9414001"
```

Load the daily meteorological input data (P, Temp, and PET) and the observed discharge at the catchment outlet as a single `data.frame` object, covering the period from 01-Jan-1979 to 31-Dec-2016:

```
data(Trancura9414001)
```

Create individual time series for P, PET, and Qobs:

```
dates <- Trancura9414001[, 1]
P      <- Trancura9414001[, 2]
PET    <- Trancura9414001[, 4]
Qobs   <- Trancura9414001[, 5]
```

It is important to distinguish between model simulation and model calibration. To **run** GR4J, observed discharge values at the catchment outlet are not required. However, to **calibrate** the model, observed discharge values must be available at the same temporal frequency as the simulated values, because they are needed to compute the user-defined goodness-of-fit measure between the model simulations and their corresponding observations.

Transform the previously created numeric values and their corresponding dates into `zoo` objects:

```
dates      <- as.Date(dates)
P.zoo      <- zoo(P, dates)
PET.zoo    <- zoo(PET, dates)
Qobs.zoo   <- zoo(Qobs, dates)
```

Daily discharges simulated by GR4J are expressed in mm/day, whereas the observed discharges loaded above are in m^3/s . Therefore, before comparing observations with simulations, the observed discharge values must be converted from m^3/s to mm/day:

```
# 1 day = 86400 s
Qobs.zoo <- (Qobs.zoo * 1000 * 86400) / Area.m2
```

Plot the full time series of meteorological input data (P, PET) and observed discharge (Qobs):

```
par(mfrow=c(3,1))
plot(P.zoo, xlab="Time", col="lightblue", main="Precipitation", ylab="P [mm/day]")
grid()
plot(PET.zoo, xlab="Time", col="darkgreen", main="Potential evaporation", ylab="PET [mm/day]")
grid()
plot(Qobs.zoo, xlab="Time", col="blue", main="Observed streamflows", ylab="Q, [mm] ")
grid()
```


Figure 1: Daily values of precipitation, potential evapotranspiration and streamflows for the Trancura River Basin during the 1970-2016 time period.

8.4 Model parameters

It is not a requirement for `hydroPSO`, but setting the names of the `airGR` model parameters will make easier the interpretation of the calibration results. In addition, we need to define the lower and upper boundaries for each one of the parameters of the model.

One option is to follow the ranges reported by Perrin et al. (2003):

```
names <- c("X1", "X2", "X3", "X4")
lower <- c( 100,  -5,  20,  -1.1)
upper <- c(1200,  3,  300,  2.9)

names(lower) <- names
names(upper) <- names
```

Alternatively, a very wide parameter range could be used:

```
boundaries <- matrix(c(+9.99, +9.99, +9.99, +9.99,
                      -9.99, -9.99, -9.99, -9.99),
                    ncol = 4, byrow = TRUE)
boundaries <- TransfoParam_GR4J(ParamIn = boundaries, Direction = "TR")
lower      <- boundaries[2, ]
upper     <- boundaries[1, ]

names(lower) <- names
names(upper) <- names
```

However, a very wide parameter range may require a very large number of model runs before an acceptable *best* parameter set is found. It may also allocate many particles to hydrologically implausible regions of the search space, reducing the efficiency of the calibration experiment.

Based on a non-exhaustive experiment, this vignette uses a parameter range that is wider than the one suggested by Perrin et al. (2003) but narrower than the very wide range shown above:

```
names <- c("X1", "X2", "X3", "X4")
lower <- c( 0, -100,  0,  0)
upper <- c(1200,  100, 5000,  5)

names(lower) <- names
names(upper) <- names
```

8.5 Wrapper R function implementing GR4J for hydroPSO

For the calibration of `GR4J`, or any other hydrological model implemented as an R function, an R wrapper function must be created to connect the model with `hydroPSO`. This wrapper evaluates a candidate parameter set, runs the hydrological model, computes the objective function, and returns the information required by `hydroPSO` to guide the swarm through the parameter space. **This function MUST fulfil the following requirements:**

- 1) Its first argument must be named **param.values**, representing the numeric values of the parameters to be optimised.
- 2) One of its arguments must be named **obs**, representing the observed values used to evaluate the simulated streamflow generated by the hydrological model.
- 3) It must return a list object with, at least, the following elements:
 - 3.1) **GoF**: the goodness-of-fit value obtained when the hydrological model is run with **param.values** as the parameter set.

3.2) **sim**: the model output obtained when the hydrological model is run with **param.values** as the parameter set. It MUST have the same object class and dimensions as the observed values provided by the user in **obs**.

This wrapper-function design is one of the main reasons why **hydroPSO** is useful beyond a single model. Once the interface is defined, the same optimisation engine can be applied to other hydrological models, objective functions, transformations, or calibration periods with limited changes to the surrounding workflow.

8.5.1 Required variables

airGR does not use **zoo** objects as model inputs; it works with plain numeric vectors and explicit date information. Therefore, the input time series must be transformed into numeric objects before running **GR4J**:

```
P <- as.numeric(P.zoo)
PET <- as.numeric(PET.zoo)
Qobs <- as.numeric(Qobs.zoo)
```

Because **airGR** is a *suite* of hydrological models, running **GR4J** requires a few preparatory objects that specify the selected model, input data, warm-up period, and simulation period.

Before running **GR4J**, at least the following variables must be defined:

- 1) **FUN_MOD**: R function defining the hydrological model to be executed (e.g. `RunModel_GR4J`, `RunModel_GR5J`, `RunModel_GR6J`, `RunModel_CemaNeigeSWAT+`).
- 2) **DatesR**: `POSIXt` object defining the dates corresponding to the precipitation and potential evapotranspiration time series used as **numeric** model inputs. Daily dates stored as `Date` objects can be transformed into `POSIXt` objects using the `as.POSIXt` function.
- 3) **InputsModel**: `InputsModel` object storing the daily precipitation and potential evapotranspiration, dates and R-based function used to run the **GR4J** hydrological model. For more information see `?CreateInputsModel`.
- 4) **IndPeriod_WarmUp**: numeric index identifying the portion of the input meteorological time series (see `?CreateInputsModel`) to be considered as *warm-up* period. For more information see `?CreateRunOptions`.
- 5) **IndPeriod_Run**: numeric index identifying the portion of the input meteorological time series (see `?CreateInputsModel`) to be used to run the model and return the output object. The output object will have the same temporal extent as the period identified by `IndPeriod_Run`. For more information see `?CreateRunOptions`.
- 6) **RunOptions**: `RunOptions` object (a particular type of list), created with the `CreateRunOptions` function, containing all the data required to compute the model outputs (e.g., `IndPeriod_WarmUp`, `IndPeriod_Run`, `IniStates`)

```
# dates for the full time period (calibration + verification)
dates <- time(P.zoo)

# Numeric index with the position of the warm-up period and the calibration period wrt 'dates'
WarmUpPeriod.index <- seq( pmatch(Warmup.Ini.Cal, dates), pmatch(Warmup.Fin.Cal, dates) )
CalPeriod.index <- seq( pmatch(Cal.Ini, dates), pmatch(Cal.Fin, dates) )

# Inputs required by the GR4Jmodel: P, PET, dates, GR4J
modelInputs <- CreateInputsModel(FUN_MOD= RunModel_GR4J,
                                DatesR= as.POSIXt(dates),
                                Precip= P, PotEvap= PET
                                )
```

```

runOptions.CAL <- CreateRunOptions(FUN_MOD= RunModel_GR4J,
                                  InputsModel= modelInputs,
                                  IndPeriod_WarmUp= WarmUpPeriod.index,
                                  IndPeriod_Run= CalPeriod.index
                                  )

## Warning in CreateIniStates(FUN_MOD = FUN_MOD, InputsModel = InputsModel, :
## 'RunModel_GR4J' does not require 'ExpStore'. Value set to NA

## Warning in CreateIniStates(FUN_MOD = FUN_MOD, InputsModel = InputsModel, :
## 'RunModel_GR4J' does not require 'IntStore'. Values set to NA

## Warning in CreateIniStates(FUN_MOD = FUN_MOD, InputsModel = InputsModel, :
## 'RunModel_GR4J' does not require 'GCemaNeigeLayers' 'GCemaNeigeLayers',
## 'GthrCemaNeigeLayers' and 'GlocmaxCemaNeigeLayers'. Values set to NA

Qobs.zoo.cal <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Cal.Ini, end=Cal.Fin)
dates.cal <- time(Qobs.zoo.cal)

```

8.5.2 Minimal hydromodInR function

The package-level `hydromodInR()` function is used below for direct diagnostic runs. With the current interface, a single named numeric vector can be passed directly through `Particles`; `hydromodInR()` converts it internally to a one-row parameter set, injects it into `model.FUN.args` as `param.values`, and then calls the user-defined `GR4J_hydromodInR()` model function. The model function itself contains only the GR4J-specific `airGR` call and the goodness-of-fit calculation.

```

GR4J_hydromodInR <- function(param.values,
                              InputsModel,
                              RunOptions,
                              FUN_MOD,
                              obs,
                              dates = time(obs),
                              gof.FUN = "KGE",
                              gof.FUN.args = list(method = "2012")
                              ) {

  # Running the GR4J model
  modeloutput <- RunModel(Param = param.values,
                          InputsModel = InputsModel,
                          RunOptions = RunOptions,
                          FUN_MOD = FUN_MOD
                          )

  # Getting the outputs simulated by the GR4J model
  sim <- zoo(as.numeric(modeloutput$Qsim), dates)

  # Computing model's performance
  gof.args <- modifyList(gof.FUN.args, list(sim = sim, obs = obs))
  gof <- do.call(gof.FUN, gof.args)

  # Creating the output of the R function
  out <- list(GoF = gof, sim = sim)

  return(out)
} # 'GR4J_hydromodInR' END

```

The arguments that remain fixed across all calibration-period model runs are stored in `model.FUN.args`. This list is passed unchanged to `hydroPSO()` later. In direct diagnostic calls, the candidate parameter vector is passed directly to `hydromodInR()` through `Particles`:

```
model.FUN.args <- list(InputsModel = modelInputs,
                      RunOptions = runOptions.CAL,
                      FUN_MOD = RunModel_GR4J,
                      obs = Qobs.zoo.cal,
                      dates = dates.cal,
                      gof.FUN = "KGE",
                      gof.FUN.args = list(method = "2012")
                    )
```

8.6 Running airGR

The `hydromodInR()` function can now be called directly for simple diagnostic runs before calibration. This keeps the preliminary model checks consistent with the same evaluation path that will later be used internally by `hydroPSO`.

8.6.1 Average parameter set

Before calibrating GR4J, it is good practice to verify that the model runs correctly with the prepared input data. As a first diagnostic run, the parameter set is defined as the midpoint between the lower and upper bounds of each model parameter:

```
params <- lower + (upper - lower) / 2
modeloutput <- hydromodInR(param.values = params,
                           model.FUN = GR4J_hydromodInR,
                           model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args)
```

The output returned by `hydromodInR()` includes the simulated streamflow and the goodness-of-fit value required by `hydroPSO`:

```
str(modeloutput)
```

```
## List of 2
## $ GoF: num 0.645
## $ sim:'zoo' series from 1980-01-01 to 1997-12-31
## Data: num [1:6575] 4.74 4.63 4.53 4.43 4.34 ...
## Index: Date[1:6575], format: "1980-01-01" "1980-01-02" ...
```

For this example, only simulated streamflow is extracted, because it is the model output that can be directly compared with the observed discharge series loaded above:

```
Qsim.zoo.cal <- modeloutput$sim
Qsim <- as.numeric(Qsim.zoo.cal)
```

The model outputs returned by GR4J cover only the period defined by the `IndPeriod_Run` argument in `CreateRunOptions`, i.e., the period from `Cal.Ini` to `Cal.Fin`. Therefore, before comparing simulated streamflow with its observed counterpart, the observations (`Qobs`) must be subset to the same simulation period:

```
Qobs.zoo <- zoo(Qobs, dates)
Qobs.zoo.cal <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Cal.Ini, end=Cal.Fin)
```

The direct `hydromodInR()` call returns the simulated streamflow as a `zoo` object. The following object stores the associated dates for consistency with the rest of the vignette:

```
dates.cal <- time(Qsim.zoo.cal)
```

Graphical comparison between the **daily** observed and simulated time series obtained with the *average* parameter set:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ylab="Q, [mm]", lty=c(1, 1), cex=0.4)
```


Figure 2: Evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

This first diagnostic run is useful, but the low-flow behaviour can still be improved. The next step is to evaluate a parameter set included in Coron & Michel (2025).

8.6.2 (pseudo) *Default* parameter set

There is no single *default* parameter set for GR4J (Coron & Michel, 2025). Therefore, as a second diagnostic run, this tutorial uses a parameter set provided in the example of the `CreateRunOptions` function in the manual of the `airGR` R package (Coron & Michel, 2025):

```
params      <- c(X1=734.568, X2=-0.840, X3=109.809, X4 = 1.971)
names(params) <- names

modeloutput <- hydromodInR(param.values = params,
                           model.FUN   = GR4J_hydromodInR,
                           model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args)
```

Extract only the simulated streamflow from the full model output:

```
Qsim.zoo.cal <- modeloutput$sim
Qsim         <- as.numeric(Qsim.zoo.cal)
```

The direct `hydromodInR()` call returns the simulated streamflow as a `zoo` object. The following object stores the associated dates for consistency with the rest of the vignette:

```
dates.cal <- time(Qsim.zoo.cal)
```

Graphical comparison between the **daily** observed and simulated time series obtained with this reference parameter set:

```
ggof( sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ylab="Q, [mm]", lty=c(1, 1), cex=0.4)
```


Figure 3: Evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

This parameter set improves the simulation relative to the previous diagnostic run, but there is still substantial room for improvement through formal calibration.

9 Calibrating GR4J with hydroPSO

9.1 Subsetting for the calibration period

For the calibration of GR4J with hydroPSO, only part of the available input time series is used. The remaining period is reserved for independent verification, which provides a more robust assessment of the calibrated parameter set:

```
P.zoo.cal <- window(P.zoo , start=Warmup.Ini.Cal, end=Cal.Fin)
PET.zoo.cal <- window(PET.zoo , start=Warmup.Ini.Cal, end=Cal.Fin)
```

Because the model outputs returned by GR4J cover only the period defined by the `IndPeriod_Run` argument in `CreateRunOptions`, i.e., the time period from `Cal.Ini` to `Cal.Fin`, the observations (`Qobs`) must be subset to the same simulation period before they are compared with the simulated streamflows:

```
Qobs.zoo <- zoo(Qobs, dates)
Qobs.zoo.cal <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Cal.Ini, end=Cal.Fin)
```

Store the dates associated with the period used to evaluate the calibration outputs:

```
dates.cal <- time(Qobs.zoo.cal)
```

9.2 Running the calibration

The GR4J model can now be calibrated with hydroPSO using `fn = "hydromodInR"` and the `model.FUN.args` list defined above:

```
out <- hydroPSO(fn = "hydromodInR",
               lower = lower, upper = upper, method = "sps2011",
               control = list(drty.out = PSO.drty.out, write2disk = TRUE,
                             MinMax = "max", npart = 40, maxit = 50,
                             normalise = TRUE, REPORT = 10,
                             parallel = "none", reltol = 1E-10),
               model.FUN = GR4J_hydromodInR,
               model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args
               )
```

In the previous code chunk, the arguments passed to `hydroPSO` are briefly explained below (more information can be found with `?hydroPSO`):

- a) **fn**: character string used to tell `hydroPSO` that it will optimise an R-based hydrological model.
- b) **lower**: numeric vector defining the lower boundaries of the model parameters.
- c) **upper**: numeric vector defining the upper boundaries of the model parameters.
- d) **method**: character string defining the PSO algorithm used to calibrate the hydrological model.
- e) **model.FUN**: R function used to run the hydrological model, returning model simulations and their corresponding goodness-of-fit value while fulfilling the three requirements mentioned in Section 9.2.
- f) **model.FUN.args**: list object containing all arguments used to run the hydrological model, in addition to **param.values**.
- g) **control**: list object containing the arguments used to fine-tune the calibration with `hydroPSO`. The arguments passed to **control** affect how `hydroPSO` explores the parameter space and how optimisation outputs are written. Particular attention should be given to the following:
 - *drty.out*: character, with the full path to directory that will store the output files of `hydroPSO`, only used when `write2disk=FALSE`. By default `drty.out="PSO.out"` which is looked for within the

current working directory. If `drty.out` does not exist, it is automatically created by `hydroPSO` with an informative warning message.

- `write2disk`: logical, indicates whether the output files will be written to the disk or not. By default `write2disk=TRUE`. If you are only interested in the *optimum* parameter set found by `hydroPSO` and the corresponding simulated values obtained when running `SWAT+` with that parameter set, you should set `write2disk=FALSE`, to reduce the storage used in your computer and to reduce the total computation time (because internal files are not written to disk). However, if you set `write2disk=FALSE` you will not be able to use the `plot_results` function, because it requires the internal files created by `hydroPSO` when `write2disk=TRUE`.
- `MinMax`: character string indicating whether the calibration solves a maximisation or minimisation problem. Valid values are `c('min', 'max')`. The default value is `"min"`.
- `npart`: numeric value defining the number of particles in the swarm. By default, `npart=NA`, which means that the swarm size depends on the selected method: `npart=ceiling(10+2*sqrt(n))3` when `method='sps02007'`, or `npart=40` otherwise.
- `maxit`: numeric, maximum number of iterations. By default `maxit=1000`.
- `Xini.type`: character, indicates how to initialise the particles' positions in the swarm within the ranges defined by `lower` and `upper`. By default `Xini.type='random'` (random initialisation of positions). However, you might want to try `Xini.type='lhs'` (Latin Hypercube initialisation), or `Xini.type='sobol'` (since `hydroPSO>=0.6`, for quasi-random initialisation of particle's positions using uniform Sobol low discrepancy numbers).
- `boundary.wall`: sometimes PSO fails to keep particles within the valid search space. This argument addresses this by defining exactly how out-of-bounds particles are managed. The specific values it can take are:
 - `NA`: The default setting. It automatically applies either `absorbing2007` or `absorbing2011` depending on the chosen optimisation method.
 - `absorbing2011`: Clamps the particle's position to the boundary edge but flexibly modifies its velocity, allowing it to smoothly 'slide' along the wall rather than stopping completely.
 - `absorbing2007`: A strict clamp that locks the particle to the edge and zeroes its velocity. The particle remains stuck without momentum until algorithmic forces pull it back inside.
 - `reflecting`: Acts as a perfectly elastic surface. It mirrors the particle back inside and exactly reverses its velocity, preserving kinetic energy for continuous, aggressive exploration.
 - `damping`: Functions as an inelastic collision. It reflects the particle back into the space but applies a random reduction to its reversed velocity to bleed off kinetic energy and prevent endless oscillation.
 - `invisible`: Mathematically ignores the boundaries, allowing particles to fly freely outside without altering position or velocity. Out-of-bounds fitness is not evaluated; the particle relies on the attraction of its historical bests to eventually return.
- `normalise`: logical, indicates whether the parameter values have to be normalised to the `[0,1]` interval during the optimisation or not. It is recommended to use this option when the search space is not an hypercube. By default `normalise=FALSE`.
- `reltol`: numeric, relative convergence tolerance. By default `reltol=sqrt(.Machine$double.eps)`, typically, about `1e-8`.
- `REPORT`: numeric, indicates the frequency of report messages printed to the screen. Default to every 100 iterations. Only used when `verbose=TRUE`.
- `parallel`: character, indicates how to parallelise `hydroPSO`. By default `parallel="none"`. Other possible values are: `parallel="parallel"` (for unix-alike machines) and `parallel="parallelWin"` (for MS Windows machines).

³`n` is the number of model parameters being calibrated.

- *par.nnodes*: numeric, indicates the number of cores/CPU's to be used in the local multi-core machine, or the number of nodes to be used in the network cluster. By default `par.nnodes=NA`, which assigns `par.nnodes=parallel::detectCores()` only when `parallel!="none"`.
- *par.pkgs*: list of package names (as characters) that need to be loaded on each node for allowing the objective function `fn` to be evaluated. By default `par.pkgs=list()`. Used only when `parallel="parallelWin"`.

The maximum number of model evaluations during calibration is approximately `npart * maxit`, and the **total execution time** depends on both the cost of one model run and the number of evaluations required by the optimisation. This makes the choice of swarm size (`npart`) and the maximum number of iterations (`maxit`) a practical compromise between search robustness and computational cost.

Using `npart=40` should be good enough for most model applications. However, if the number of parameters of your model is ~ 10 or more, I suggest to **explore the use of a larger number of particles in combination with a lower number of model runs** (e.g., `npart=80` and `maxit=50`). This later ensures that `hydroPSO` will have enough number of particles to effectively tackle the *curse of dimensionality*, and help to reduce premature convergence, which is particularly relevant for hydrological models affected by parameter interactions, threshold behaviour, and equifinality.

9.3 Basic analysis of calibration results

Inspect the *best* parameter set obtained during calibration and its corresponding goodness-of-fit value:

```
# 'best' parameter set obtained during calibration
out$par

##           X1           X2           X3           X4
## 1195.780809    8.017508   352.181058    1.909790

# goodness-of-fit obtained for the 'best' parameter set
out$value

## [1] 0.8589189
```

Save the *best* parameter set obtained during calibration:

```
best.param.cal <- out$par
```

The variables required to run `GR4J` were defined earlier (i.e., `InputsModel` and `RunOptions`). The model can now be run with the *best* parameter set obtained during calibration:

```
modeloutput <- hydromodInR(param.values = best.param.cal,
                           model.FUN = GR4J_hydromodInR,
                           model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args)
```

Extract the simulated streamflow returned by `hydromodInR()`:

```
Qsim.zoo.cal <- modeloutput$sim
```

Define a customised title for the following figures:

```
main <- paste0("GR4J: ", Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
```

Graphical comparison between the **daily** observed and simulated time series obtained with the *best* parameter set for the calibration period, excluding the warm-up period:

```

#Qsim.zoo.cal <- window(Qsim.zoo.cal, start=Cal.Ini)
#Qobs.zoo.cal <- window(Qobs.zoo.cal, start=Cal.Ini)
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.3, lty=c(1,1) )

```


Figure 4: Graphical comparison of streamflows simulated by extttGR4J during the calibration period using several performance indices.

The calibrated parameter set produces a clearer improvement relative to the preliminary diagnostic runs based on average and reference parameter values.

Graphical comparison between **daily** and **monthly** simulated ($Q_{sim.zoo.cal}$) and observed ($Q_{obs.zoo.cal}$) values for the calibration period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ftype="dm",
     FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 5: Daily and monthly evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

Graphical comparison between the **monthly** and **annual** simulated and observed values for the calibration period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ftype="ma", pt.style="bar",
     FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 6: Monthly and annual evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

Graphical comparison between the **seasonal** simulated and observed values for the calibration period, with one plot for each season:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ftype="seasonal", ylab="Q, [mm]",
     season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
     FUN=mean, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 7: Seasonal evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

Computing the **daily residuals** for the calibration period:

```
residuals <- Qsim.zoo.cal - Qobs.zoo.cal
```

Plot **daily**, **monthly**, and **annual** time series, boxplots, and histograms of the residuals for the calibration period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, var.unit="mm")
```


Figure 8: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the calibration period at the daily, monthly, and annual temporal scales.

Plot **seasonal** time series and boxplots of the **residuals** for the calibration period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, pfreq="seasonal",
          season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
          h=0, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 9: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the calibration period at the seasonal scale.

9.4 Plotting calibration results

Define a customised title for all figures in this section:

```
main <- paste0("GR4J: ", Qobs.stationname, " (" , Qobs.ID, ")")
```

9.4.1 Basic plotting

The function `plot_results`, included in `hydroPSO`, can automatically produce several diagnostic figures to support the evaluation of calibration results. Internally, it calls `read_results` and then generates figures that summarise parameter distributions, objective-function behaviour, convergence, and the agreement between observed and simulated values. These diagnostics are useful because they move the calibration analysis beyond a single best value and help identify parameter interactions, equifinality, and possible structural limitations of the model. The function can produce the following eleven (11) figures:

- 1) Dotty plots of parameter values.
- 2) Histograms of parameter values.
- 3) Boxplots of parameter values.
- 4) Correlation matrix among parameter values (optional).
- 5) Empirical CDFs of parameter values.
- 6) Parameter values vs Number of Model Evaluations.
- 7) (pseudo) 3D dotty plots of (selected) parameter values.
- 8) GoF for each particle against the Number of Model Evaluations.
- 9) Velocity values vs Number of Model Evaluations.
- 10a) Scatterplot between Best Simulated values and Observations (OPTIONAL, only if `MinMax` is provided).
- 10b) Empirical CDFs for model output (only produced if `obs` is NOT a zoo object).
- 10b) ggof (See `?ggof`) between Best Simulated values and Observations (OPTIONAL, only if `obs` is a zoo object).
- 10d) Empirical CDFs for selected quantiles of model output (OPTIONAL, only if `obs` is a zoo object).
- 11) Convergence Measures (`Gbest` and `normSwarmRadius`) vs Iteration Number.

Basic automatic plotting of the calibration results to the current graphics device, usually the screen, can be obtained with:

```
plot_results(drty.out=PS0.drty.out)
```

9.4.2 Advanced plotting

Although the automatic plotting of calibration results may be sufficient for many applications, it is advisable to read `?plot_results` and customise its arguments to obtain figures that meet the needs of a specific study, report, or publication:

```
plot_results(drty.out=PSO.drty.out, # directory that stores all the calibration outputs
            do.png=TRUE,           # plots go to PNG figures instead of to the screen
            params.png.width=630,  # 7 inches equals 630 pixels at 90 DPI. 900
            params.png.height=630, # 7 inches equals 630 pixels at 90 DPI. 1500
            MinMax="max",          # 'best' parameter set is the one with the highest GoF
            beh.thr=0.3,           # behavioural parameter sets (with GoF >= 0.3 )
            ftype="dm",            # to produce daily and monthly figures of 'sim' vs 'obs'
            nrows=2,               # number of rows in parameter figures (histograms,...)
            FUN=mean,              # function used to compute monthly values
            do.pairs=TRUE,         # correlation plot among parameters and GoF
            gof.name="KGE2012",    # name used for axis titles in parameter figures
            legend.pos="right",    # position of the legend in the convergence plot
            main=main              # user-defined title for most of the output figures
        )
```

```
## [                               ]
## [      Reading output files ... ]
## [                               ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 2000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 1821 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Velocities.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 2000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 1821 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Model_out.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 2000 ]
## [ Number of model outputs for each parameter set ('nsim'): 6575 ]
## [ Number of behavioural model outputs           : 1821 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'ConvergenceMeasures.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of iterations: 50 ]
## [ Number of iterations with Gbest >= 0.3: 50 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles_GofPerIter.txt' ... ]
## [ Number of particles : 40 ]
```

```

## [ Number of iterations: 50 ]
## [                               ]
## [           Plotting ...       ]
## [                               ]
## [ Plotting convergence measures into 'ConvergenceMeasures.png' ... ]
##
## [ Plotting dotty plots for parameter values into 'Params_DottyPlots.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting histograms for parameter values into 'Params_Histograms.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting boxplots for parameter values into 'Params_Boxplots.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting correlation matrix for parameter values into 'Params_Pairs.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting empirical CDFs for parameter values into 'Params_ECDFs.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting parameter values vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Params_ValuesPerRun.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting 3D dotty plots for parameter values into 'Params_dp3d.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting GoF for each particle vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Particles_GofPerIter.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting velocity values vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Velocities_ValuePerRun.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting best simulated values vs observations into 'ModelOut_BestSim_vs_Obs-Corr.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting best simulated values vs observations into 'ModelOut_BestSim_vs_Obs-ggof.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting ECDFs of simulated quantiles vs observations into 'ModelOut_Quantiles.png' ... ]
## [ Computing un-weighted quantiles for each ROW of 'sim' ... ]
## |                               |

```

The figures generated by the previous call to `plot_results` are **not discussed in detail in this tutorial**. They are provided as examples of the diagnostic material that `hydroPSO` can generate automatically to support scientific reporting and model evaluation. Additional discussions of these outputs can be found in Rojas & Zambrano-Bigiarini (2012), Zambrano-Bigiarini & Rojas (2013), Abdelaziz & Zambrano-Bigiarini (2014), and Abdelaziz et al. (2019).

9.4.2.1 Convergence along iterations

This figure shows the change in the **objective function** (black line) and the change in the **normalised swarm radius** (a measure of swarm spread on the search space) along with the number of iterations used in the optimisation. This figure can be used to obtain a founded guess about the minimum number of iterations required to obtain a satisfactory value of the objective function.

Figure 10: Evolution of global optimum (i.e., KGE2012) and the normalized swarm radius against the number of iterations.

9.4.2.2 Histograms

This figure shows **histograms** of parameter values considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation.

GR4J: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Figure 11: Histograms of user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$) versus parameter values. The vertical red line indicates the optimum parameter value. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

9.4.2.3 Boxplots

This figure shows **boxplots** of parameter values considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The horizontal red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation.

Figure 12: Box-and-whisker plots (or boxplots) of user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$) versus parameter values. The horizontal red line indicates the optimum parameter value found during the optimisation. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

9.4.2.4 Dotty plots

This figure shows **dotty plots** of parameter values versus the objective function, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation, whereas the horizontal red line shows the corresponding best model performance.

GR4J: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Figure 13: Dotty plots showing the model performance of behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$) versus parameter values. The vertical red line indicates the optimum parameter value found during the optimisation, whereas the horizontal red line shows the corresponding best model performance. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

9.4.2.5 Empirical CDFs

This figure shows **empirical CDFs** of parameter values, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets (`KGE2012 >= beh.thr`). Horizontal grey dotted lines represent a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (median of the distribution). Vertical grey dotted lines represent the parameter value corresponding to a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (its value is shown in the upper part of each figure).

GR4J: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Figure 14: Empirical CDFs (continuous black lines) of parameter values. Horizontal gray dotted lines represent a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (median of the distribution). Vertical gray dotted lines represent the parameter value corresponding to a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (its value is shown in the upper part of each figure).

9.4.2.6 3D dotted plots

This figure shows a scatter-based diagnostic plot (aka **pseudo three-dimensional dotted plots**) to explore the relationship between pairs of model parameters and a goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh. thr}$). Regions with blue (red) colours illustrate parameter ranges where the interaction of two parameters lead to high (low) model performance. This function is particularly useful in hydrological modelling to assess parameter interactions, equifinality, and behavioural regions after calibration or Monte Carlo simulation.

Figure 15: Three-dimensional dotted plots to explore the relationship between pairs of model parameters and the goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric.

9.4.2.7 Correlation matrix

This figure shows **correlation matrix** between parameters and model performance (KGE2012), considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE2012 \geq \text{beh. thr}$). Horizontal and vertical axes show the physical range used for the calibration of each parameter. Red curved lines represents are fitted to all the pair of points using a lowess smoother, i.e., a locally-weighted polynomial regression.

Figure 16: Correlation matrix between parameters and model performance (KGE2012). Horizontal and vertical axes show the physical range used for the calibration of each parameter. Red curved lines are fitted to all pairs of points using a lowess smoother, i.e., a locally-weighted polynomial regression.

9.4.2.8 Daily and monthly evaluation

This figure shows a **comparison of daily** (upper panel) and **monthly** (lower panel) **streamflows**, obtained with the *best* parameter set obtained during the optimisation, against their corresponding observed counterparts.

Figure 17: Comparison of daily (upper panel) and monthly (lower panel) streamflows obtained with the 'best' parameter set and their corresponding observed counterparts.

9.4.2.9 Scatterplot of daily values

This figure shows a **Scatterplot** comparing observed streamflows against the simulated values obtained with the *best* parameter set obtained during the optimisation.

Figure 18: Scatterplot of daily streamflows obtained with the 'best' parameter set obtained during calibration and their corresponding observed counterparts.

9.4.2.10 Evaluation of low, medium and high streamflows

This figure shows **empirical CDFs** (blue lines) for 5, 50 and 95 quantiles of simulated discharges obtained by GR4J during the calibration period. The previous quantiles were selected as representative of low, medium and high streamflows, respectively. Vertical black-dotted lines represent the observed 5, 50 and 95 quantiles, while vertical grey-dotted lines indicate the median of the simulated quantiles. Therefore, this figure is useful to assess the bias of model results in the low, medium and high part of the simulates time series.

Figure 19: Empirical CDFs (blue lines) for 5, 50 and 95 quantiles of simulated discharges obtained by extttGR4J during the calibration period. Vertical black-dotted lines represent the observed quantiles, while vertical grey-dotted lines indicate the median of the simulated quantiles.

9.5 Uncertainty analysis of calibration results

If you are not familiar with uncertainty analysis, you might be interested in Refsgaard et al. (2007), who review the terminology and typology of uncertainty, its interaction with the broader water management process and the role of uncertainty at different stages in the modelling processes.

9.5.1 Reading all calibration results

To proceed with the uncertainty analysis, read the calibration results generated by `hydroPSO` during the optimisation. In this tutorial, the focus is on **behavioural parameter sets** (Beven, 2006; Beven & Binley, 1992; Beven & Freer, 2001), defined here by an arbitrary user-selected goodness-of-fit threshold. For this example, `beh.thr=0.3` is used. Setting `beh.thr=0.3` and `MinMax='max'` considers as behavioural all parameter sets with goodness-of-fit values higher than the selected threshold:

```
PSO.drty <- paste0(model.drty, "/PSO.out/")
res      <- read_results(drty.out=PSO.drty, MinMax="max", beh.thr=0.3)

## [ ]
## [ Reading output files ... ]
## [ ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 2000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 1821 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Velocities.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 2000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 1821 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Model_out.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 2000 ]
## [ Number of model outputs for each parameter set ('nsim'): 6575 ]
## [ Number of behavioural model outputs : 1821 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'ConvergenceMeasures.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of iterations: 50 ]
## [ Number of iterations with Gbest >= 0.3: 50 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles_GofPerIter.txt' ... ]
## [ Number of particles : 40 ]
## [ Number of iterations: 50 ]
```

The next code chunk assigns all the behavioural parameter sets obtained during calibration (*params*), i.e., those with goodness-of-fit value higher than `beh.thr`; the goodness-of-fit value of each behavioural parameter set (*gofs*), the model outputs (i.e., streamflows for the GR4J case) corresponding to each behavioural parameter set (*Qsims*), the model output corresponding to the best parameter set obtained during calibration (*model.best*), and the observed values used in the calibration to compute the goodness-of-fit value (*model.obs*):

```
params    <- res[["params"]]
gofs     <- res[["gofs"]]
Qsims    <- res[["model.values"]]
model.best <- res[["model.best"]]
model.obs <- res[["model.obs"]]
```

9.5.2 Weighted quantiles of parameter values

Weighted quantiles of model parameters provide an estimate of parameter uncertainty based on the behavioural parameter sets obtained during calibration and their corresponding goodness-of-fit values. User-defined weighted quantiles for each model parameter are obtained by multiplying the standard quantile derived for each model parameter based on all the behavioural parameter sets (i.e., for each column in `params`) by the corresponding goodness-of-fit value obtained by the parameter set (*gofs*)⁴. In this tutorial, the `wquantile` function from `hydroPS0` is used to compute the 2.5, 50, and 97.5 weighted quantiles for each model parameter, by setting `probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975)`:

```
params.025.50.975 <- wquantile(params, weights=gofs, byrow=FALSE, probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975),
                               normwt=TRUE, verbose=FALSE)
```

It may be useful to compare the *best* parameter set found during calibration with the median of the weighted behavioural parameter sets. In the following code chunk, a new column is added to `params.025.50.975`, immediately after the median (quantile 50):

```
params.025.50.best.975 <- cbind(params.025.50.975[, c(1,2)],
                                Best=as.numeric(best.param.cal),
                                params.025.50.975[, 3] )
colnames(params.025.50.best.975)[4] <- "97.5%"
round( params.025.50.best.975, 2)
```

FALSE	2.5%	50%	Best	97.5%
FALSE X1	32.02	675.87	1195.78	1174.38
FALSE X2	-34.34	12.13	8.02	41.20
FALSE X3	414.30	1210.03	352.18	3881.22
FALSE X4	0.18	1.69	1.91	3.88

9.5.3 Weighted quantiles of model simulations

Weighted quantiles of model simulations provide an estimate of uncertainty for each model-simulated value (i.e., each daily streamflow), using the goodness-of-fit values obtained for the complete simulated time series. User-defined weighted quantiles for each model simulation are obtained by combining the ensemble of simulations in `Qsims` with their corresponding goodness-of-fit values in `gofs`. In this tutorial, the `wquantile` function from `hydroPS0` is used to compute the 2.5, 50, and 97.5 weighted quantiles for each value simulated by the model, by setting `probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975)`:

```
Qsim.025.q50.q975 <- wquantile(Qsims, weights=gofs, byrow=FALSE, probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975),
                               normwt=TRUE, verbose=FALSE)
```

⁴For more information about the computation of the weighted quantiles, please read `?wtd.stats`.

```
round( head(Qsim.025.q50.q975), 3)
```

```
FALSE      2.5%   50% 97.5%
FALSE Sim1 2.955 5.070 8.238
FALSE Sim2 2.847 4.922 8.079
FALSE Sim3 2.741 4.775 7.897
FALSE Sim4 2.651 4.642 7.727
FALSE Sim5 2.563 4.512 7.567
FALSE Sim6 2.489 4.388 7.407
```

To plot the uncertainty bounds for each model-simulated value, transform the weighted quantiles 2.5 and 97.5 into zoo objects:

```
dates.cal <- dip(Cal.Ini, Cal.Fin)
q025      <- zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,1], dates.cal)
q975      <- zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,3], dates.cal)
```

9.5.4 P-factor and R-factor

Compute the **P-factor** (Abbaspour et al., 2009; Schuol et al., 2008), which represents the percentage of observations that are within the user-defined uncertainty bounds:

```
( pf <- pfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )
```

```
## [1] 0.904943
```

Compute the **R-factor** (Abbaspour et al., 2009; Schuol et al., 2008), which represents the average width of the user-defined uncertainty bounds divided by the standard deviation of the observations:

```
( rf <- rfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )
```

```
## [1] 1.229108
```

A good model should bracket most of the measured data (i.e., large P-factor, with a maximum of 1) with the smallest possible R-factor (minimum of 0).

9.5.5 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)

The *best* simulated streamflows can now be plotted along with the **95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)** (Abbaspour et al., 2007, 2009; Schuol et al., 2008):

```
main.uncert <- paste0("Uncertainty bounds GR4J: ",
                     Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
Qobs.col     <- "black"
best.sim.col <- "blue"
bands.col    <- "lightblue"

Qsim.best.zoo <- zoo(model.best, time(Qobs.zoo.cal) )
```

```
plot(Qobs.zoo.cal, xaxt="n", xlab="", type="n", main=main.uncert, ylab="Q, [mm]") # empty plotting area
drawTimeAxis(Qobs.zoo.cal) # time axis
plotbandsonly(lband=q025, uband=q975) # 95 PPU
lines(Qobs.zoo.cal, col=Qobs.col, lwd=0.3) # Qobs
lines(Qsim.best.zoo, col=best.sim.col, lwd=0.3) # best simulation
```

```

grid()

legend("topright", legend=c("Qobs", "best.sim", "95PPU"), lty=c(1, 1, NA),
      pch=c(NA, NA, 15), col=c(Qobs.col, best.sim.col, bands.col),
      bty="n", cex = 1.2)

legend("topleft", legend=c(paste0("P-factor: ", round(pf, 2)),
                           paste0("R-factor: ", round(rf, 2)) ),
      bty="n", cex = 1.2)

```


Figure 20: 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU) for model simulations during the calibration period.

9.5.6 Uncertainty in flow duration curve

Use the `fdcu` function included in the `hydroTSM` R package to plot the observed flow duration curve (FDC), the FDC of the *best* simulated streamflow, and the flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the calibration period:

```

main.uncert <- paste0("Flow duration curves GR4J model: ", Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
bands.col   <- "lightskyblue1"

par(mfrow=c(3,1))
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.best.zoo, bands.col=bands.col,
     main=main.uncert, log="") # empty plotting area
grid()
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.best.zoo, bands.col=bands.col,
     main=main.uncert, log="y") # empty plotting area
grid()
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.best.zoo, bands.col=bands.col,
     main=main.uncert, log="x") # empty plotting area
grid()

```

Flow duration curves GR4J model: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Flow duration curves GR4J model: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Flow duration curves GR4J model: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Figure 21: Flow duration curve of the observed (black line) and best simulated (blue line) streamflows. In addition, flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the calibration period. The upper panel is the normal flow duration curve, the middle panel has focus on low flows ($\log='y'$) and the lower panel has focus on high flows ($\log='x'$).

9.5.7 Some comments about P-factor and R-factor

GLUE-like uncertainty analysis (Beven, 2006; Beven et al., 2008; Beven & Binley, 1992) is sensitive to the threshold value used to select behavioural parameter sets (`beh.thr`). Lower threshold values generally retain more parameter sets and therefore produce wider uncertainty bounds for the posterior distribution of parameters and model simulations (Jin et al., 2010).

Usually, lower `beh.thr` values increase the P-factor because more observations are bracketed by the uncertainty bounds, but this comes at the expense of a higher R-factor. The threshold should therefore be selected with care, considering the purpose of the analysis, the quality of the observations, the model structure, and the hydrological signatures of interest.

10 Verification analysis

10.1 Basic analysis of the verification period

To proceed with the verification analysis, the temporal duration of the verification period (i.e., from `Ver.Ini` to `Ver.Fin`) and the corresponding warm-up period must first be defined. The full meteorological record spans 1979-2016, whereas the verification period selected for this example covers 1999-2016. Therefore, the period from 1979-01-01 to 1998-12-31 is used as the warm-up period:

```
# dates corresponding to the verification period,)
dates.ver <- dip(Ver.Ini, Ver.Fin)

# Numeric index with the position of the warm-up period and the calibration period wrt 'dates'
WarmUpPeriod.index <- seq( pmatch(Warmup.Ini.Cal, dates), pmatch(Warmup.Fin.Ver, dates) )
VerPeriod.index     <- seq( pmatch(Ver.Ini, dates), pmatch(Ver.Fin, dates) )

# Inputs required by the GR4Jmodel: P, PET, dates, GR4J
modelInputs      <- CreateInputsModel(FUN_MOD= RunModel_GR4J,
                                       DatesR= as.POSIXlt(dates), Precip= P, PotEvap= PET)

runOptions.VER <- CreateRunOptions(FUN_MOD= RunModel_GR4J,
                                   InputsModel= modelInputs,
                                   IndPeriod_WarmUp= WarmUpPeriod.index,
                                   IndPeriod_Run= VerPeriod.index)

## Warning in CreateIniStates(FUN_MOD = FUN_MOD, InputsModel = InputsModel, :
## 'RunModel_GR4J' does not require 'ExpStore'. Value set to NA
## Warning in CreateIniStates(FUN_MOD = FUN_MOD, InputsModel = InputsModel, :
## 'RunModel_GR4J' does not require 'IntStore'. Values set to NA
## Warning in CreateIniStates(FUN_MOD = FUN_MOD, InputsModel = InputsModel, :
## 'RunModel_GR4J' does not require 'GCemaNeigeLayers' 'GCemaNeigeLayers',
## 'GthrCemaNeigeLayers' and 'GlocmaxCemaNeigeLayers'. Values set to NA

Qobs.zoo.ver <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Ver.Ini, end=Ver.Fin)

model.FUN.args.ver <- modifyList(
  model.FUN.args,
  list(
    InputsModel = modelInputs,
    RunOptions = runOptions.VER,
    obs = Qobs.zoo.ver,
    dates = dates.ver
  )
)
```

```
)  
)
```

Run GR4J with the *best* parameter set obtained during calibration for the verification period, using the same direct `hydromodInR()` setup and the verification-specific `model.FUN.args.ver` list:

```
modeloutput <- hydromodInR(param.values = best.param.cal,  
                             model.FUN = GR4J_hydromodInR,  
                             model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args.ver)
```

Extract the simulated streamflow returned by `hydromodInR()`:

```
Qsim.zoo <- modeloutput$sim
```

The model outputs returned by GR4J cover only the period defined by the `IndPeriod_Run` argument in `CreateRunOptions`, i.e., the time period from `Ver.Ini` to `Ver.Fin`. Therefore, before comparing simulated streamflow with its observed counterpart, the observations (`Qobs`) must be subset to the same verification period:

```
Qsim.zoo.ver <- Qsim.zoo # just for using the same variable names afterwards
```

Graphically compare the daily observed and simulated time series obtained with the *best* parameter set for the verification period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.3, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 22: Graphical comparison of observed and simulated streamflow time series obtained with the **best** parameter set obtained during the calibration.

This first visual inspection provides a direct assessment of whether the calibrated parameter set transfers satisfactorily to the independent verification period.

Graphically compare **daily** and **monthly** simulated ($Q_{sim.zoo.ver}$) and observed ($Q_{obs.zoo.ver}$) values for the verification period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, ftype="dm",
     FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 23: Daily and monthly evaluation of simulated streamflows for the verification period using several performance indices.

Graphically compare **monthly** and **annual** simulated and observed values for the verification period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, ftype="ma", pt.style="bar",
     FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 24: Monthly and annual evaluation of simulated streamflows for the verification period using several performance indices.

Graphically compare **seasonal** simulated and observed values for the verification period, with one plot for each season:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, ftype="seasonal", ylab="Q, [mm]",
     season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
     FUN=mean, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 25: Seasonal evaluation of simulated streamflows for the verification period using several performance indices.

Compute the **daily residuals** for the verification period:

```
residuals <- Qsim.zoo.ver - Qobs.zoo.ver  
residuals <- window(residuals, start=Ver.Ini)
```

Plot daily, monthly, and annual time series, boxplots, and histograms of the **residuals for the verification** period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, var.unit="mm")
```


Figure 26: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the verification period at the daily, monthly, and annual temporal scales.

Plot **seasonal** time series and boxplots of the residuals for the verification period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, pfreq="seasonal",
          season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
          h=0, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 27: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the verification period at the seasonal scale.

10.2 Running behavioural parameter sets

One advantage of the GR4J implementation in `airGR` is that model inputs and run options can be redefined for the independent verification period without changing the model function. The object `model.FUN.args.ver`, defined above, updates the period-specific elements of `model.FUN.args` and is reused by `verification()`.

Since `hydroPSO` v0.5-0, the `verification` function is fully compatible with R-based hydrological and environmental models. It can therefore be used to **run the model with all behavioural parameter sets** obtained during calibration. This makes it possible to obtain the full time series of simulated values associated with each behavioural parameter set during the verification period, which is essential for uncertainty analysis and robustness assessment:

```
out <- verification(fn = "hydromodInR",
  par = params,
  control = list(gof.name = "KGE2012", # Only used for plot titles
    MinMax = "max", # Are we looking for a minimum or maximum?
    do.plots = FALSE,
    write2disk = TRUE,
    parallel = "none",
    verbose = TRUE),
  model.FUN = GR4J_hydromodInR,
  model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args.ver
)
```

In the previous code chunk, the arguments passed to `verification` have the same meaning as those of `hydroPSO` (more information can be found with `?verification`), with the exception of:

-) `par`: `data.frame` with all the parameter sets that will be run with GR4J. In this case, `params` was already read using a behavioural threshold equal to `beh.thr`.

10.3 Uncertainty analysis of verification results

10.3.1 Reading all verification results

To proceed with the uncertainty analysis, read all verification results generated by the previous call to the `verification` function:

```
gofs <- out[["gofs"]]
Qsims <- out[["model.values"]]
best.param.ver <- out[["best.param"]]
best.gof <- out[["best.gof"]]
```

10.3.2 Weighted quantiles of model simulations

Weighted quantiles of model simulations provide an estimate of predictive uncertainty for each model-simulated value, i.e., for each daily streamflow. The weights are based on the goodness-of-fit values obtained during verification for each complete simulated time series. User-defined weighted quantiles for each model simulation are obtained by combining the ensemble of simulations in `Qsims` with the corresponding goodness-of-fit values in `gofs`. In this tutorial, the `wquantile` function from `hydroPSO` is used to compute the 2.5, 50, and 97.5 weighted quantiles for each simulated value, by setting `probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975)`:

```
Qsim.025.q50.q975 <- wquantile(Qsims, weights=gofs, byrow=FALSE, probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975),
  normwt=TRUE, verbose=FALSE)
round( head(Qsim.025.q50.q975), 3)
```

```
FALSE      2.5%   50% 97.5%
```

```
FALSE sim1 0.648 1.440 2.924
FALSE sim2 0.638 1.421 2.896
FALSE sim3 0.627 1.406 2.877
FALSE sim4 0.618 1.392 2.857
FALSE sim5 0.611 1.380 2.831
FALSE sim6 0.604 1.366 2.809
```

To plot the uncertainty bounds for each value simulated during the verification period, transform the weighted quantiles 2.5 and 97.5 into zoo objects:

```
dates.ver <- dip(Ver.Ini, Ver.Fin)
q025      <- zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,1], dates.ver)
q975      <- zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,3], dates.ver)
```

10.3.3 P-factor and R-factor

Compute the **P-factor** (Abbaspour et al., 2009; Schuol et al., 2008), which represents the percentage of observations that are within the user-defined uncertainty bounds:

```
( pf <- pfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )
## [1] 0.8787833
```

Compute the **R-factor** (Abbaspour et al., 2009; Schuol et al., 2008), which represents the average width of the user-defined uncertainty bounds divided by the standard deviation of the observations:

```
( rf <- rfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )
## [1] 1.100172
```

A good model should bracket most of the measured data (i.e., large P-factor, with a maximum of 1) with the smallest possible R-factor (minimum of 0).

10.3.4 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)

The *best* simulated streamflows obtained during verification can now be plotted along with the **95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)** (Abbaspour et al., 2007, 2009; Schuol et al., 2008):

```
main.uncert <- paste0("Uncertainty bounds GR4J: ",
                      Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
Qobs.col     <- "black"
best.sim.col <- "blue"
bands.col    <- "lightblue"

plot(Qobs.zoo.ver, xaxt="n", xlab="", type="n", main=main.uncert, ylab="Q, [mm]") # empty plotting area
drawTimeAxis(Qobs.zoo.ver) # time axis
plotbandsonly(lband=q025, uband=q975) # 95 PPU
lines(Qobs.zoo.ver, col=Qobs.col, lwd=0.3) # Qobs
lines(Qsim.zoo.ver, col=best.sim.col, lwd=0.3) # best simulation during the verification
grid()

legend("topright", legend=c("Qobs", "best.sim", "95PPU"), lty=c(1, 1, NA),
       pch=c(NA, NA, 15), col=c(Qobs.col, best.sim.col, bands.col),
```

```

    bty="n", cex = 1.2)

legend("topleft", legend=c(paste0("P-factor: ", round(pf, 2)),
                             paste0("R-factor: ", round(rf, 2)) ),
      bty="n", cex = 1.2)

```


Figure 28: 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU) for model simulations during the verification period.

10.3.5 Uncertainty in flow duration curve

Use the `fdcu` function included in the `hydroTSM` R package to plot the observed flow duration curve (FDC), the FDC of the *best* simulated streamflow, and the flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the verification period:

```

main.uncert <- paste0("Flow duration curves GR4J model: ", Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
bands.col   <- "lightskyblue1"

par(mfrow=c(3,1))
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, bands.col=bands.col,
     main=main.uncert, log="") # empty plotting area
grid()
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, bands.col=bands.col,
     main=main.uncert, log="y") # empty plotting area
grid()
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, bands.col=bands.col,
     main=main.uncert, log="x") # empty plotting area
grid()

```

Flow duration curves GR4J model: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Flow duration curves GR4J model: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Flow duration curves GR4J model: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Figure 29: Flow duration curve of the observed (black line) and best simulated (blue line) streamflows. In addition, flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the verification period. The upper panel is the normal flow duration curve, the middle panel has focus on low flows (log='y') and the lower panel has focus on high flows (log='x').

11 FAQ

11.1 How can I parallelise my computations?

In hydroPSO, parallel execution is controlled through the `parallel` element of the `control` list passed to `hydroPSO`. For R-based models such as GR4J, this can reduce computing time when the model function is sufficiently expensive or when a large swarm and many iterations are used.

The following two code chunks illustrate how to run the same calibration without and with parallel computation. They use the minimal model function defined earlier and keep the same calibration settings, so that the difference is restricted to the execution mode.

```
parallel <- "none"
write2disk <- FALSE
set.seed(1000)
( t1 <- system.time(
  out <- hydroPSO(fn="hydromodInR",
    lower=lower, upper=upper, method="sps2011",
    control=list(write2disk=write2disk, MinMax="max", npart=40,
      maxit=50, normalise=TRUE, REPORT=10,
      parallel=parallel, reltol=1E-10),
    model.FUN = GR4J_hydromodInR,
    model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args
  )
)
)
```

```
## user system elapsed
## 5.217 0.021 5.310
```

```
parallel <- "parallel"
write2disk <- FALSE
set.seed(1000)
( t2 <- system.time(
  out <- hydroPSO(fn="hydromodInR",
    lower=lower, upper=upper, method="sps2011",
    control=list(write2disk=write2disk, MinMax="max", npart=40,
      maxit=50, normalise=TRUE, REPORT=10,
      parallel=parallel, reltol=1E-10),
    model.FUN = GR4J_hydromodInR,
    model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args
  )
)
)
```

```
## user system elapsed
## 10.221 5.806 5.711
```

The total reduction in the *elapsed times* (see `?proc.time`) when comparing the previous two running R processes was (as percentage):

```
reduction <- as.numeric(round(100 * (t1["elapsed"] - t2["elapsed"]) / t1["elapsed"], 1))
( paste0(reduction, "%") )
```

```
## [1] "-7.6%"
```

The previous difference in execution time was important, because `hydroPSO` was executed without writing the output files to the hard drive and because single run of the `GR4J` model is quite fast. This reduction in computation time can make an even more important difference for hydrological models with long running times.

Of course, for the same hydrological model and host machine, the total reduction in computation time will increase with increasing values of `par.nnodes`. However, if the value of `par.nnodes` is not so high (six or less), **the use of `parallel!=none` might not be a good idea**, because of the overhead associated to the communication between the cores/nodes and the main algorithm.

You can also run `verification` in parallel using the same previous approach:

```
out <- verification(fn = "hydromodInR",
  par = params,
  control = list(gof.name = "KGE2012", # Only used for plot titles
    MinMax = "max", # Are we looking for a minimum or maximum?
    do.plots = FALSE,
    write2disk = TRUE,
    parallel = "parallel",
    par.nnodes = 5,
    par.pkgs = c("hydroPSO", "hydroGOF", "hydroTSM",
      "zoo", "data.table"),
    verbose = TRUE),
  model.FUN = GR4J_hydromodInR,
  model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args.ver
)
```

11.2 Why do I get some warnings after the calibration?

Warnings are often related to parameter sets that produce non-finite simulations, poor model performance, or numerical conditions that are outside the meaningful range of the hydrological model. In calibration experiments, some particles may visit regions of the parameter space that are hydrologically implausible even if they remain inside the numerical bounds defined by the user. The relevant point is to inspect whether the optimisation completed successfully and whether the final behavioural parameter sets produce meaningful streamflow simulations.

In the previously described cases, some parameter sets return `NA` when used to run `GR4J`. You might want to have a look to the `./PSO.out/Particles.txt` and `./PSO.out/Model_out.txt` files, to get the values of the parameter sets and the model outputs, respectively, that returned `NA` values.

If you want to reduce the number of warnings, you might explore to change some of the following `control` arguments: `Xini.type`, `boundary.wall...`

11.3 Why the KGE values shown by `ggof` do not match the one obtained during the optimisation?

The objective function used during optimisation may evaluate a specific period, transformation, or subset of the data, whereas `ggof` may compute its statistics over the time series provided to the plotting function. Small discrepancies can also arise when warm-up periods, missing values, or unit conversions are handled differently. For this reason, the objective-function definition used inside the wrapper function should be considered the reference value for the calibration experiment.

11.4 Why do I get different results every time that I run hydroPSO with the same input data?

Particle Swarm Optimisation is a stochastic population-based algorithm. Unless the random-number generator is initialised with a fixed seed before calling `hydroPSO`, different runs may start from different initial swarms and may therefore produce different trajectories through the parameter space. To improve reproducibility, use `set.seed()` before running the calibration and report the main calibration settings, including parameter bounds, swarm size, number of iterations, objective function, and stopping criteria.

12 Software details

This tutorial was built under:

```
## [1] "aarch64-apple-darwin23"  
## [1] "R version 4.6.0 (2026-04-24)"  
## [1] "hydroPS0 0.5-58"  
## [1] "airGR 1.7.8"  
## [1] "hydroGOF 0.7-0"  
## [1] "hydroTSM 0.8-6"  
## [1] "zoo 1.8-15"
```

13 Version history

-) v0.5: May 31th, 2026
-) v0.4: May 27th, 2026
-) v0.3: April 28th, 2020
-) v0.2: April 27th, 2020
-) v0.1: March 16th, 2020

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